

Why Red State and Trump Policies
Do Not Explain Trans Decline

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Courage
Freedom
Truth

Executive Summary

- The decline of trans identity among young Americans took place as or more rapidly in states the Democrats won in 2024 than in Republican states
- The decline of trans identity among young Americans took place as or more rapidly on liberal campuses as on conservative ones
- Student ideology did not shift right between 2023 and 2025, when trans and queer identification declined
- Students did not become less woke on culture war issues between 2023 and 2025, when trans and queer identification declined
- Trans identity has declined faster on campuses where mental health improved most between 2023 and 2025
- However, most of the change in gender identity is not accounted for by improvements in mental health

Introduction

Trans is in decline among young Americans, but this is *not* the result of a new climate of Trumpian intolerance. Following my recent [report](#), viral tweet [thread](#) and [article](#) on the decline of trans and queer identification among young American students, Jean Twenge conducted an analysis of trends of the wider non-student population.¹ Her results confirmed the trend, and most now accept that transgender – whether binary or non-binary - is a rapidly declining identity among young Americans. Twenge also confirmed some of the generational patterns I spotted in the FIRE data, whereby the youngest are less trans than older Gen-Z students.

With many conceding the argument that trans is in decline among young Americans, some progressive commentators claim that the decline in willingness to identify as trans is the result of Trump's anti-trans policies and conservative pressure. Observing the declining numbers of non-binary students at Brown, Samantha Riedel at *Them* [writes](#) that, 'One major contributing factor could be the political climate at Brown. In July this year, Brown signed an agreement with the Trump administration in order to maintain federal funding, under which the university agreed to adopt the government's strictly binary view of "biological sex" for all policy purposes and to refrain from providing gender-affirming care through its medical program.'

More broadly, the argument that greater toleration is what has enabled higher rates of LGBTQ+ identification is known as the minority stress hypothesis.² The theory also argues that discrimination and conformist pressure accounts for the well-documented higher rates of mental illness among gender and sexual minorities.

Is rising minority stress, caused by Trump's clampdown on transwomen's access to women's spaces, and on youth gender transition surgery, at the root of the decline of trans? Short answer: no.

The first point to note is that American students remain overwhelmingly liberal, and this has not changed much during the 6 years for which we have FIRE data. Figure 1 shows that American students at major universities break about 5:2 liberal versus conservative. Though there was a modest step-increase in moderates over 2022-23, there is no rightward shift during the critical years 2023-25 when trans and queer went into decline.

¹ Kaufmann, E. 2025. '[The Decline of Trans and Queer Identity among Young Americans](#),' *Centre for Heterodox Social Science*, Report No. 5; Twenge, Jean, '[Trans identification really is in free fall: new data](#),' *Generation Tech*, Oct 20, 2025

² Meyer, I. H. (1995). "Minority stress and mental health in gay men." [Journal of health and social behavior](#): 38-56.

Figure 1

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25.

It's the same story at Andover Phillips Academy, another of my data sources. The current balance is around 55-15 liberal to conservative. If anything, as Figure 2 shows, the liberal advantage has gone up in the very years that trans and queer identification have gone down.

Figure 2

Source: Andover Phillips Academy annual student surveys, 2016-2025.

As I mentioned in my previous report, the proportion of students identifying with a religion (as distinct from no religion) has remained flat. Moreover, as Figure 3 reveals, there is stability in the proportion of students who want to keep anti-trans speakers off campus – around 80 percent – and the share who believe shouting down

offensive speakers is acceptable. If anything, the intolerance on campus concerns those who criticize trans, not those who identify with it.

Figure 3

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25.

Even so, might it be the case that non-binary students feel under pressure from their peers to remain in the closet? I should add here that I use non-binary as a proxy for transgender because non-binary is classified by transactivists as part of trans, and because Twenge's work shows non-binary and transgender identification trends to be correlated.

The first thing to say is that the trans share is higher in more liberal student bodies, but there is a wide spread of trans identification rates at each level of ideology. Figure 4 pools data across 2020-25 and shows the relationship. Liberty and Hillsdale have almost no non-binary students whereas liberal arts colleges such as Smith, Oberlin and Bard have nearly 20 percent non-binary among their student body.

This relationship arises mainly out of individual-level relationships: nearly 40 percent of trans students identify as very liberal compared to 17 percent of students overall. The correlation in Figure 4 is partly an artefact of trans students tending to identify as liberal, especially as very liberal (point 1 on the 7-point self-ascribed ideology scale).

And yet, most of the trans phenomenon is not accounted for by political ideology. For instance, there is a 15-

point difference in non-binary share between equally liberal Pomona College and Bard College.

Figure 4

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25.

Are trans students increasingly reluctant to express themselves? We would expect this if minority threat was on the rise among trans students. Yet the evidence suggests otherwise.

To measure this, I examine self-censorship trends among trans and other students over time. From 2021, FIRE surveys asked the question, ‘On your campus, how often have you felt that you could not express your opinion on a subject because of how students, a professor, or the administration would respond?’ Response categories are as follows:

- 1) Never
- 2) Rarely
- 3) Occasionally
- 4) Fairly often, a couple times a week
- 5) Very often, nearly every day

17 percent of students during 2021-25 ticked options 4 or 5, indicating that they engaged in high self-censorship of their views.

It is certainly the case that trans students self-censor more on conservative campuses than on liberal ones. This relationship holds even when controlling for the fact that liberal students – as most trans students are - self-censor more on conservative campuses, and vice-versa.

Even with parameters for sexual orientation and other demographics in a statistical model predicting the likelihood of self-censoring, trans students self-censor more in more conservative (or less highly liberal) environments.

Figure 5 shows the relationship between campus ideology and trans students' self-censoring, which exhibits a mild slope, indicating a real - if moderate - correlation between average campus liberal-conservative ideology and non-binary students' mean level of self-censorship. Trans students self-censor their views more at conservative Liberty and Brigham Young than at liberal Vassar or Mount Holyoke.

Hillsdale is an outlier in that almost none of its non-binary students self-censor. Even so, since there are only 10 such students in the Hillsdale sample, this may just be the luck of the draw rather than reflecting an unusually open speech climate at Hillsdale. Likewise, the University of California at Santa Barbara has very liberal students but quite high trans self-censorship. There is a large spread of average college self-censorship rates at each level of average college ideology. The lion's share of the phenomenon of non-binary students self-censoring is not explained by their campus ideological environment.

Figure 5

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25.

Be this as it may, the ecological fallacy recognizes that trends over time do not necessarily reflect relations between individuals. Just as rich states may vote Democratic even as rich individuals do not, more trans time periods such as 2022 may be no more liberal than less trans time periods like 2025 even if trans individuals are much more liberal than other students.³

Bearing this in mind, let us examine what has occurred with self-censorship over time. Figure 6 shows the self-censorship rate among students from various groups between 2021 and 2025 (years this question was asked). Rates of self-censorship have decreased over time for both non-binary and queer/bisexual students (pink sets of time series), even if the thaw in speech climate for them in the past 3 years is not as substantial as it has been for conservative students.

Even with the freer speech climate of 2025, a quarter of conservative students say they self-censor regularly, which is considerably higher than the equivalent figure for non-binary and queer/bisexuals - who report self-

³ Firebaugh, G. (1980). "Cross-national versus historical regression models: conditions of equivalence in comparative analysis." *Comparative Social Research* 3: 333-344.

self-censorship rates of 14-17 percent: at or below the 17 percent student average for 2025.

In short, conservatives are considerably more likely than trans students to be in the closet while the latter are no more likely to censor themselves than the average student.

Figure 6

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25.

When asked whether it is difficult for them to speak about transgender issues, Figure 7 shows that half of conservatives say this is difficult, with little change over 2020-25. Non-binary students are *less* likely than those who identify as male or female to say it is difficult to speak about trans issues.

Once again, conservatives are in the closet much more than non-binary students, who actually feel freer than the average student to speak their mind.

Figure 7

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25.

Figure 8 considers whether non-binary identification has declined more in liberal or conservative environments.

If the minority stress hypothesis is accurate, we should see more of a decline on conservative campuses.

Figure 8 shows that in colleges whose students lean conservative (average of 4 to 7 on a 7-point ideology scale), such as North Dakota State or Brigham Young, there has been a rise and fall in trans identity, while at the more liberal colleges (scoring 3 or less on average on a 7-point scale) we find a similar rise and fall pattern. This is also true of the Ivy League, whose elite students lean strongly liberal. In short, there is no evidence that trans identification has followed a different trajectory on conservative campuses than on liberal ones.

Finally, the trend towards trans decline was well in train by 2024, before Trump was elected. The same trajectory is evident in Jean Twenge's reported US Census Bureau Household Pulse 2024 data and her Cooperative Election Study (CES) data for 2024-25. Developments under Trump appear to be a continuation of a pre-existing trend rather than a departure from trend.

Figure 8

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25. N= 78,398 on very liberal campuses and 32,737 on conservative campuses.

Looking at the data by red state and blue state colleges in Figure 9 shows a similar pattern, with rise and decline taking place in equal measure in both Republican and Democratic-controlled states – and with no inflection point in 2024.

Figure 9

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25. Survey data leans 65-35 to blue states.

Indeed, it is notable that, if anything, colleges whose student body shifted right during 2023-25 (according to the unweighted FIRE sample) experienced a smaller decline in non-binary identification than colleges whose student body moved left (see Figure 10). The relationship is significant, even if modest, as shown by the

downward sloping red fitted values line. There is thus no evidence that conservative peer pressure explains the decline in trans identification between 2023 and 2025.

Figure 10

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25.

Another way to look at this is to examine whether trans decline was more rapid in red states, who have been enacting legislation that is more hostile to the transactivist position on gender issues. Figure 11 shows that there is no relationship: trans did not decline more in red states than in blue states. If anything it declined less, on average, in red states – though this effect disappears when you account for the higher starting share of trans students on blue state campuses in 2023.

Figure 11

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25.

Running an Ordinary Least Squares model (to illustrate effect sizes more easily) in Figure 12 shows that those who are very liberal, have no religion, are anxious or depressed, attend a liberal-leaning college and are of lower socioeconomic class background are significantly more likely to identify as non-binary. Whites are less likely than nonwhites to do so, though the effect size is not as large as for the aforementioned factors. 2022 and 2023 were peak years for trans identification.

Whether a student is attending a college located in a red or blue state does not significantly predict whether they will identify as non-binary, though the direction is toward students being *more* likely to identify as non-binary in red state colleges than blue state colleges.

Figure 12

Source: FIRE surveys 2020-25. $R^2=.016$ for OLS; Pseudo- R^2 of .040 for Ordered Logit (coefficients similar in direction and effect size). N= 226,117.

What might have made the difference? As I mention in my report, the only correlate that seems to explain some of the change is improved mental health. Figure 13 shows a strong and significant college-level relationship over 2023-25 between declining share with anxiety and depression, and declining non-binary share. Nevertheless, all colleges saw declines in mental illness and most of this cannot be explained by the decline in non-binary share, so this is only part of the explanation (whatever the direction of causation).

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